

**NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF FLUTTER STABILITY ON A COMPRESSOR
CASCADE WITH VARIABLE INFLOW CONDITIONS**

Patrick Neumann

Technische Universität Berlin
Berlin, Germany

Valentina Motta

Technische Universität Berlin
Berlin, Germany

Leonie Malzacher

Technische Universität Berlin
Berlin, Germany

Dieter Peitsch

Technische Universität Berlin
Berlin, Germany

ABSTRACT

The effects of variable inlet flows on the aeroelastic stability of a compressor cascade are investigated. The variability is not related to a mean change of inlet flow conditions but to a spacial inhomogeneous or time varying inflow. Detailed computational fluid dynamic simulations at a variety of inhomogeneous inlet flow conditions have been carried out. Steady and unsteady inlet conditions are assessed according to the state of the art. The data has been analysed in terms of damping parameters to assess the flutter characteristic of the cascade. For the computational fluid dynamic analysis the same blade geometry and cascade parameters have been adopted as in use at the aeroelastic test facility of the Chair for Aero Engines at the Technische Universität Berlin. The results show that the steady inhomogeneous inlet flow conditions have little or almost no effect on the aeroelastic stability. On the contrary, the studied unsteady inflow conditions show significant effects on the stability. Here the phase shift between flow perturbation and blade movement is the driving parameter, deciding whether an increase or decrease of aeroelastic stability can be achieved. Furthermore, the inhomogeneous deviation to the mean flow field related to blade oscillation defines the gain or loss of stability.

INTRODUCTION

To increase the aeroelastic stability of turbomachinery blades, mistuning is widely used. For years, most of the mistuning research has been focused on structural mistuning such as blade-to-blade frequency or mode shape variations. On the contrary, limited attention has been drawn to aerodynamic mistuning such as misstaggering, uneven blade-to-blade spacing or leading edge blending. In

the work of Kielb et. al. [1] the aerodynamic influence coefficients (which are explained further in the theory part) are changed asymmetrically in the equations of motions of an representative front stage compressor rotor. For the so-called ‘symmetry group 2 perturbation’ the length of the force vector in the complex plane of even diagonal influence coefficients in the influence matrix is increased by 25% and the force vector for odd diagonal influence coefficients in the influence matrix is decreased by 25%. This resulted in a clear change of eigenfrequency and damping. Similar effects to aerodynamic mistuning occur under distorted inlet flow conditions. Herricks [2] studied the effect of a steady total pressure deviation at the inlet on the aeroelastic stability of a rotating fan. The fan blades experienced a periodic change of the incoming flow field with a frequency which was set by the author to be close to the eigenfrequency of the first torsional eigenmode. The resulting aerodynamic work showed a dependency on each blades circumferential position at the beginning of a torsional oscillation. In the work of Frey and Fleeter [3], perforated plates upstream a research compressor are implemented to study the effect of gusts on the unsteady aerodynamic force which is acting on the compressor blades. In these experiments, the torsional vibration of the blades was implemented with a fixed dependency of the circumferential position. With this experimental setup, the phase between the gust and torsional motion of the blades could be studied. It was shown that the phase alters the blade rows aeroelastic stability. Vahdati et. al. [4] studied the compressor aerodynamics for different intake ducts. Here a clear difference in flutter stability for different intake ducts was shown, which were caused by acoustic reflections. Flutter occurred when an acoustic mode matched the blade vibration in shape and frequency. Additionally Vahdati et. al. [5] showed that the upstream

traveling pressure wave is reflected at the intake and is increasing or decreasing the aeroelastic stability. The driving parameter here is the phase difference between the upstream and reflected traveling pressure wave at the studied fan face. The aim of this work is to study the influence of variable inflow conditions on the aeroelastic stability of a compressor cascade. The variability is not related to a mean change of the inlet flow field but to a local or time varying change of the inlet flow field. It is the objective to contribute to the understanding of the influence of variable inflow conditions on aeroelastic stability. Therefore, several steady and unsteady inhomogeneous inflow conditions, which are promising to affect the aeroelastic stability, are studied.

THEORY

The basic oscillation pattern of a tuned rotor are the so called traveling wave modes for each mode family. For one traveling wave mode (TWM) the blades oscillate in the same blade motion, but with a fixed phase difference between two adjacent blades, the so-called inter blade phase angle (IBPA). Each TWM is linked to a nodal diameter n , which has the relation to the IBPA presented in equation 1, N being the number of blades.

$$IBPA = \frac{360^\circ n}{N}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, N-1 \quad (1)$$

The applied mathematical model in this work is derived from the equation of motion (equation 2) for the 2D torsional mode in individual blade coordinates. The vector $\underline{\theta}$ is the vector of the blade torsional amplitudes. The terms on the left hand side describes the structural equation of motion, \underline{M} being the mass matrix and \underline{D} the damping matrix shown in equation 3, as well as \underline{K} being the stiffness matrix shown in equation 4. The values for the torsional inertia I_θ and mechanical damping g_{str} are acquired from experimental data [6]. The right hand side of equation 2 describes the aerodynamic motion dependent forces.

FIGURE 1: Moments definition for influence coefficient technique.

$$-\omega^2 \underline{M} \underline{\theta} e^{i\omega t} + i \underline{D} \underline{\theta} e^{i\omega t} + \underline{K} \underline{\theta} e^{i\omega t} = \frac{\rho}{2} V^2 c^2 \underline{CM} \underline{\theta} e^{i\omega t} \quad (2)$$

$$\underline{M} = \begin{bmatrix} I_\theta & 0 \\ & \ddots \\ 0 & I_\theta \end{bmatrix} \quad \underline{D} = \begin{bmatrix} I_\theta \omega_\theta^2 g_{str} & 0 \\ & \ddots \\ 0 & I_\theta \omega_\theta^2 g_{str} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$\underline{K} = \begin{bmatrix} I_\theta \omega_\theta^2 & 0 \\ & \ddots \\ 0 & I_\theta \omega_\theta^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The 2D approach results in the use of torsional inertia per span I_θ and aerodynamic moments per span M . The influence coefficient technique (ICT), which applies the superposition principle, is used to obtain the influence coefficients CM_m . Therefore, CFD-simulations are carried out with a sinusoidal oscillation of one blade. This results in blade moments on the oscillating blade itself and on neighbouring blades. For example the resulting moment on the blade 2 due to the oscillation of the 0th blade results in the Moment $M_{m=2} = M_2$. This is illustrated in figure 1. Consequently it is possible to fill the influence coefficient matrix in equation 6 with just one simulation, with CM_{N-m} being CM_{-m} . The motion-induced moments decay rapidly for increasing absolute values of the index m . It is therefore sufficient to acquire just the motion-induced moments on the two neighbouring blades on suction and pressure side of the oscillating blade [7, 8]. As a consequence, solely the influence coefficients $[CM_{-2}, CM_{-1}, CM_0, CM_1, CM_2]$ are taken into account.

$$CM_m = \frac{M_m}{\frac{\rho}{2} V^2 c^2 \theta} \quad (5)$$

$$\underline{CM} = \begin{bmatrix} CM_0 & CM_{N-1} & CM_{N-2} & \dots & CM_1 \\ CM_1 & CM_0 & CM_{N-1} & \dots & CM_2 \\ CM_2 & CM_1 & CM_0 & \dots & CM_3 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ CM_{N-1} & CM_{N-2} & CM_{N-3} & \dots & CM_0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The influence coefficient CM_m acting for the n -th traveling wave mode $CM_{m,n}$ is shown in equation 7. With the superposition assumption, the resulting moment coefficient for the n -th traveling wave mode can be calculated with equation 8.

$$CM_{m,n} = CM_m e^{i \frac{2\pi m n}{N}} \quad (7)$$

$$CM0_n = \sum_{m=-2}^2 CM_m e^{i\frac{2\pi m-n}{N}} \quad (8)$$

$$-\omega^2 I_\theta \bar{\theta} + \omega_\theta^2 I_\theta \bar{\theta} + i\omega_\theta^2 I_\theta g_{str} \bar{\theta} = \frac{\rho}{2} V^2 c^2 CM0_n \bar{\theta} \quad (9)$$

For comparison reasons with experimental data [9] the aeroelastic problem is formulated in the same manner as in Hennings [6]. Therefore, the mass density ratio μ , the frequency parameter λ , the inertia parameter r_θ^2 and the reduced frequency k based on full chord are introduced in equation 10. This leads to equation 11. With the resulting λ the aeroelastic damping parameter g can be calculated with equation 13. For this formulation the aeroelastic system is unstable for positive values of g and stable for negative ones.

$$\lambda = \frac{\omega_\theta^2}{\omega^2}; \quad \mu = \frac{m}{\frac{\rho}{2} c^2}; \quad r_\theta^2 = \frac{I_\theta}{m c^2}; \quad k = \frac{\omega c}{V} \quad (10)$$

$$\lambda(1 + i g_{str}) \bar{\theta} = \left(1 + \frac{CM0_n}{\mu r_\theta^2 k}\right) \bar{\theta} \quad (11)$$

$$\omega = \frac{\omega_\theta}{\sqrt{Re(\lambda)}} \quad (12)$$

$$g = \frac{Im(\lambda)}{Re(\lambda)} \quad (13)$$

SIMULATION MODEL

Computational Fluid Dynamic (CFD) simulations are carried out on a model of the aeroelastic test rig of the Chair of Aero Engines at the Technische Universität Berlin. The test rig is a low speed wind tunnel which contains a linear compressor cascade. The cascade has 11 blades, 9 blades in the middle are elastically suspended and their movement can be preset via stepper motor. The model and its boundary conditions are depicted in figure 2. The cascade has a stagger angle of 43° and a pitch-to-chord ratio of 0.75. The blades, of the NACA 65-Series, possess a chord length of 0.15m. The cascade is modelled with 7 blades, to be able to simulate exactly one wavelength for the traveling wave mode with an IBPA of 51.4° . This IBPA is of particular interest, since the aeroelastic model used here predicts this IBPA to be the most unstable one for the lowest reduced velocity (reciprocal of reduced frequency) [9]. These results are in

good agreement with the experimental data of Hennings [6]. Periodic boundary conditions on the upper and lower wall are applied to the CFD model. Another set of simulations are carried out with 5 blades to apply the influence coefficient technique. The outlet pressure is set to 102.4kPa and a velocity is defined at the inlet.

FIGURE 2: Numerical model of aeroelastic test rig [10].

The simulations are carried out with mean inflow conditions for which the system is aeroelastically unstable [6] for a homogeneous inflow (further called ‘clean case’). The spacial and temporal mean velocity is 20m/s for all considered cases. The frequency of the purely torsional oscillation is 21.4Hz. The reduced frequency is thus resulting in 1.008. The mean angle of attack is set to 2° . The amplitude of the blades oscillation is set to $\bar{\alpha} = 1^\circ$ to stay in a linear flow regime. RANS equations which are closed with the $k-\omega$ SST-turbulence model are solved with ANSYS CFX[®]. The model with 7 blades in figure 2 contains 349,020 nodes. The mesh is designed to achieve y^+ values below 5 at the blade walls.

SIMULATION PROGRAM

The inhomogeneous inflow conditions are presented in this section. The steady inflow cases and one unsteady are evaluated with the influence coefficient technique. As a result, it is possible to study directly the effect of the inhomogeneous inflow conditions on each influence coefficient.

Steady wake: As already mentioned in the introduction, Kielb et. al. [1] studied the effect of perturbations of the influence matrix in equation 6 on the aeroelastic behaviour. The results show that the perturbations achieve a change in eigenfrequency and damping. Nevertheless, it has to be determined what exactly can change the influence matrix in this way. A plausible idea is that a steady flow distortion in the blade row alters the aerodynamic influence on neighbouring blades. A possible steady disturbance can be a disturbed blade wake. Wakes from an upstream rotor blade row are disturbed through the downstream stator row, but besides that, they do not change their position relative to the downstream rotor row with the same rotational speed

for unchanged operation conditions. To be able to separate steady and unsteady effects, a steady wake distortion is studied in this work.

FIGURE 3: Blade wake positions.

The inlet velocity profile of an upstream blade wake, with the same geometry and distance from the blade row to the outlet as the modelled cascade, is simulated for different wake positions, which are described with the coordinate h shown in figure 3. The mean inlet velocity profile of one blade wake is altered with an offset to achieve an average velocity of 20m/s. The resulting flow velocity field is shown in figure 4 for a wake position of $h = 1$ on the left side and for a wake position of $h = -4$ on the right side.

FIGURE 4: Velocity field for the steady wake inflow with wake positions $h = 1$ on left side and $h = -4$ on the right side.

Unsteady velocity wave: Unsteady inhomogeneous inflow conditions need to have certain properties to be able to affect the flutter stability. Otherwise they will not result in a change of damping but in forced response. The inhomogeneous inflow needs to be blade motion dependent. Consequently the governing properties of the inhomogeneous inflow are a shape and frequency which are the same as the blade rows traveling wave movement. Furthermore, the inhomogeneous inflows have to be dependent on the blade oscillation amplitude.

FIGURE 5: Detailed geometry of one domain.

The first unsteady inhomogeneous inflow studied is the unsteady velocity wave. A spacial and time changing velocity is set at the inlet which results in an spacial and time varying total pressure field impinging at the blade row. The velocity wave and the resulting variation of total pressure match the blade rows traveling wave mode in shape and frequency. The simulations are carried out for one traveling wave mode, in detail for an inter blade phase angle of 51.4° , which is known to be the most unstable [9]. The velocity wave can be achieved by an inlet velocity distribution set by equation 14. The velocity in mean flow direction $V_{x,a}$ consist of a mean term of $V_m = 20m/s$ and a term which is changing in a sinusoidal way with time t and coordinate y . The inhomogeneous inflow is studied for several phases $\Delta\Phi$ between the velocity wave and the blade rows traveling wave oscillation. 8 different phases, which are (0° ; 45° ; 90° ; 135° ; 180° ; 225° ; 270° ; 315°), are studied to have a phase discretization of 45° . Since $\Delta\Phi$ is the phase between the velocity wave arriving at the leading edges and the blade rows oscillation, a phase convection term Φ_{tot} is added. The velocity wave is convected the distance s_a from inlet to blade row (see figure 5) in a first approximation with the mean velocity in the flow direction x_a . This leads to the definition of Φ_{tot} in equation 15. Since the blade oscillation has a phase difference of the considered IBPA with an distance of ΔY in y direction (see again figure 5), also the velocity wave has to change in this manner. This results in the phase term $\frac{IBPA}{\Delta Y} y$.

$$V_{x,a} = V_m + V_0 \sin(2\pi f_\theta t + \Delta\Phi + \frac{IBPA}{\Delta Y} y + \Phi_{tot}) \quad (14)$$

$$\Phi_{tot} = 2\pi f_\theta t_{tot} = 2\pi f_\theta \frac{s_a}{V_m} = 158^\circ \quad (15)$$

The resulting total pressure field for the velocity wave is shown in figure 6 for an IBPA of 51.4° and a phase $\Delta\Phi = 270^\circ$ between velocity wave arriving at the leading edge of the blades and the traveling wave mode of the blade row. The middle blade oscillate in a torsional manner resulting in an angle of attack of $\alpha(t) = 2^\circ + 1^\circ \sin(2\pi f_\theta t)$. For a simulation time matching a full period, which is the case for the left side of figure 6, the blades angle of attack is at the oscillations mean value. Furthermore the arriving total pressure wave in the left figure is at its minimum at the leading edge of the central blade, which is conform to a phase $\Delta\Phi = 270^\circ$. The right side of the figure shows the pressure wave after 4.25 periods. The total pressure wave traveled with the same speed as the traveling wave mode, now having a mean total pressure at the leading edge of the central blade.

FIGURE 6: Total pressure field for unsteady velocity wave as inflow condition, $IBPA = 51.4^\circ$, $\Delta\Phi = 270^\circ$, left figure: $t = 4T$, right figure: $t = 4T + 0.25T$.

Subsequently to the phase $\Delta\Phi$, also the amplitudes of the velocity wave are varied as well. The first amplitude considered is $V_0 = 0.5m/s$, representing 2.5% of the mean velocity. The lowest velocity amplitude ($V_0 = 0.0728m/s$) is representing the reflected total pressure wave studied by Vahdati et. al. [4]. For the most influential case of $\Delta\Phi$, further velocity as well as oscillation amplitudes are simulated. The vibration amplitudes being in the feasible range of the aeroelastic test rig at the Technische Universität

Berlin.

Vortex around central streamline: Another simulated inflow condition is a vortex around the central streamline further called x_a -vortex. The velocity is changed due to the vortex in the circumferential direction around the vortex core. When the vortex arrives at the leading edge of a blade, the change of the circumferential velocity, depending on the spanwise position, leads to an incidence change at this blade. This further directly influences the aerodynamic forces and moments. This is therefore a promising approach to influence the aeroelastic damping.

There are different vortex models to describe the resulting vortex velocity distribution. The potential vortex model has the disadvantage that with decreasing distance to the vortex core the velocity converge to infinity. Another vortex model is the Rankine vortex, which consist of one part up to a certain distance to the vortex core with a velocity distribution of a rotating rigid body. For distances greater than this, a velocity distribution of the potential vortex applies. The disadvantage of this model is the kink point in the velocity distribution, which does not occur naturally. Another vortex model without these disadvantages is the Lamb Oseen vortex described in equation 16. It does not possess the disadvantages of the two other models and is valid as a solution of the Navier-Stokes-Equations. Because of this reasons the velocity distribution for the Lamb Oseen vortex is used further to simulate the x_a -vortex. The circumferential velocity around the vortex core of the Lamb Oseen vortex and the other mentioned vortices is plotted against the distance to the vortex core r in figure 7. The analytical description for the Lamb Oseen vortex is given by equation 16, V_θ being the circumferential velocity in dependency of the circulation Γ_0 , the distance to the vortex core r and the Rankine radius r_0 . The circumferential velocity maximum is set by the Rankine radius at $1.121r_0$.

$$V_\theta = \frac{\Gamma_0}{2\pi r} (1 - e^{-\frac{r^2}{r_0^2}}) \quad (16)$$

For the test case, with a spanwise blade length of $s = 0.197m$ a Rankine radius of $r_0 = 0.011m$ is used. To be able to compare the results with the inhomogeneous inflow condition of the velocity wave, the vortex circulation is adapted to get a maximum circumferential velocity at the inlet of $V_{\theta,max} = 0.5m/s$. The x_a -vortex cases are calculated with a 3D CFD model, resulting from a spanwise extrusion of the already introduced 2D CFD model to a width of $0.197m$. This represents the geometry of the aeroelastic test rig at the Technische Universität Berlin. The effects of the spanwise edges of the blades as well as friction of the side walls are neglected. Hence, just an area, which is unaffected by these effects for an fully turbulent flow, is considered for the results. The considered spanwise region is therefore defined by $(0.25s < z < 0.75s)$ [9]. The spanwise coordinate

FIGURE 7: Vortex models.

z , starting at the left side wall going to the other one is also shown in figure 8. Here the resulting stationary x_a -vortex is also illustrated.

FIGURE 8: Streamlines for stationary x_a -vortex.

Next to a stationary x_a -vortex, also an unsteady case is simulated. Here the circumferential velocity at the inlet and consequently the vortex circulation is varied in time governed by equation 17. The maximum circumferential velocity of this sinusoidal temporal change is $V_{\theta,max} = 0.5m/s$ and the lowest is $V_{\theta,min} = 0m/s$. The frequency of the oscillating circulation matches the traveling wave mode frequency. The simulation parameter $\Delta\Phi$ shall again be the phase between unsteady inflow at the leading edge and blade oscillation. Therefore the convection term Φ_{tot} , being the same as in the case of the velocity wave, is added. Simulations are carried out for 8 different $\Delta\Phi$, resulting again in a phase discretization of 45° . The relation between circulation and torsional blade oscillation for $\Delta\Phi = 90^\circ$ is illustrated

in figure 9. In this case the circulation is leading the blade oscillation 90° . The positive circulation leads to an increased incidence angle for spanwise positions lower than midspan ($z < 0.5s$) and a decreased incidence for higher spanwise positions. For $\Delta\Phi = 90^\circ$, this effect has its maximum a quarter period before the maximum angle of attack occurs.

$$\Gamma(t) = \Gamma_0(0.5 + 0.5 \sin(2\pi f_{\theta}t + \Delta\Phi + \Phi_{tot})) \quad (17)$$

FIGURE 9: Unsteady x_a -vortex with $\Delta\Phi = 90^\circ$.

The stationary x_a -vortex is evaluated by the influence coefficient technique. The unsteady x_a -vortex is evaluated by the influence coefficient technique as well as by a simulation for a single traveling wave mode for comparison reasons.

Validation: The 2D model for the clean case is validated against experimental results of the aeroelastic test rig at the Technische Universität Berlin as shown in [9]. This is appropriate since the experimental results showed just neglectable 3D effects over a wide spanwise area. Based on the grid for the validated 2D clean case, a grid dependency study is carried out for the inhomogeneous inflow with the highest velocity gradients, which is the case for the steady wake inflow. Simulations with different grids are carried out for several representative wake positions. The error between two meshes is defined as mean square error normalized by the root mean square value. The reference grid for the 2D model with 5 blades consist of 249,300 nodes. The fine grid for the same model has 987,260 nodes and the finest 2,179,450 nodes. The resulting errors are listed in table 1. These deviations are close to 3% for all cases and are not significantly different for the fine and finest mesh. All values are in an acceptable range and the reference grid is therefore used further.

TABLE 1: Grid discretization errors in comparison for different refinements and wake positions.

ΔCM	$h=7$	$h=1$	$h=-1$	$h=-3$	$h=7$
ref./fine	3.13%	3.08%	3.14%	3.16%	3.14%
ref./finest	3.12%	3.09%	-	3.14%	-

Sensitivity studies with regard to time steps and simulations cycles have been carried out with the reference

grid for the unsteady inhomogeneous inflow conditions of the simulation program. The results show that the best trade-off between accuracy and computational resources is reached for 150 time steps per oscillation and simulation times of 10 times the oscillation period.

RESULTS

Steady wake: At first, the results for the steady wake inflow are presented. Since this case was evaluated with the influence coefficient technique, it is possible to calculate the damping for all inter blade phase angles. In figure 10, the damping parameter is plotted against the inter blade phase angle for all positive values of the wake position h . The negative values of the wake position are simulated as well. They show less quantitative effect and are therefore not shown for all IBPA. Additionally is the clean case plotted in figure 10. One can see the natural s-shape damping curve for the clean case, which is not changed for the inhomogeneous inflow. The steady wake inflow has just slight effects on the damping. The system is still unstable near the most unstable IBPA for the clean case at 51.4° . The systems overall aeroelastic stability is defined by the most unstable IBPA. This case is therefore studied in more detail.

FIGURE 10: Damping for different steady wake inflow positions plotted against IBPA.

In figure 11, the resulting damping parameter is plotted against the wake positions for the most unstable case of an IBPA of 51.4° . With this illustrated narrower damping range, a clear influence of the wake position becomes visible. The damping is nearly constant for four different areas. In detail the difference between the case with a wake inflow $\Delta g = g - g_{ref}$ and the clean case is nearly constant for $h = -24$ to $h = -16$, $h = -13$ to $h = -1$, $h = 3$ to $h = 11$ and $h = 18$ to $h = 24$. Each area is characterised by wakes laying between two different blades. In between those areas, a transition exists where the damping converges to the damping level of the adjacent area. For increasing h starting from $h = 11$ the damping increases as well, even the adjacent damping area is lower. This effect is greatest for $h = 14$. Here the wake is convected directly to blade -1, leading to the

conclusion that the blades proximity is the cause. However, for a traveling wave mode the blade -1 is oscillating as well and changes the leading edge position with time.

FIGURE 11: Damping for different steady wake inflow positions for an IBPA of 51.4° .

Further insight into the steady wake influence can be obtained from the influence coefficients depicted in figures 12, 13 and 14. The influence coefficient $CM_{m,IBPA}$ is the influence coefficient CM_m acting for a traveling wave mode with the corresponding IBPA. The relation to CM_m is given by equation 18, which is the same as equation 7 just using the IBPA instead of the nodal diameter.

FIGURE 12: Derived influence coefficients CM_m for the clean case and effective influence coefficients for an IBPA of 51.4° , $CM_{m,IBPA}$.

$$CM_{m,IBPA} = CM_m e^{i \frac{IBPA \pi m}{180^\circ}} \quad (18)$$

Figure 12 shows the influence coefficients for the clean case in the complex plane. The circumferential positions of

the influence coefficients changes for different IBPA (except for CM_0 or $IBPA=0^\circ$) and the distance to the origin stays the same. The important parameter for the aeroelastic stability is the imaginary part of $CM_{m,IBPA}$. For an IBPA of 51.4° , as depicted in figure 12, the influence coefficient $CM_{1,IBPA}$ has a destabilizing effect and $CM_{0,IBPA}$ a stabilizing. The other influence coefficients just have small distances to the origin and therefore do play a minor role for the stability.

FIGURE 13: Change of effective influence coefficient $CM_{1,IBPA}$ ($IBPA = 51.4^\circ$) for different wake positions.

FIGURE 14: Change of effective influence coefficient $CM_{0,IBPA}$ ($IBPA = 51.4^\circ$) for different wake positions.

The influence of the wake on CM_1 is shown in figure 13. The highest decrease of the destabilizing imaginary part is achieved for positions $h = 2$ to $h = 14$. For $h = 0$ the wake is convected directly to blade 0. This leads again to a distribution against the trend with a destabilizing peak. The influence of the wake for different positions on the other damping driving influence coefficient CM_0 is shown in figure 14. This influence coefficient, derived from the moment on the oscillating blade itself, is mainly influenced in a destabilizing way by wakes being convected to the area

between the oscillating blade and the adjacent blade on the pressure side. Also here a deflection of the imaginary part is seen for $h = 0$.

The steady wake is evaluated with the influence coefficient technique to be able to separate the effects on the influence coefficients. For a traveling wave mode a wake laying between an oscillating blade and the adjacent blade on the pressure side is also a wake on the suction side of this adjacent blade, also oscillating. To calculate the damping of the traveling wave, the wakes influences have to be added up, which leads to even smaller effects of the steady wake.

Unsteady velocity wave: The unsteady velocity wave is simulated for a traveling wave mode with the most unstable inter blade phase angle for the clean case ($IBPA=51.4^\circ$). This traveling wave mode is simulated for 8 phases $\Delta\Phi$ between the velocity wave at the leading edges and the blade rows traveling wave mode, for two amplitudes of the velocity wave V_0 . At first the results for an amplitude of $V_0 = 0.0728m/s$ are shown in figure 15. Here the damping parameter g is plotted against the phase $\Delta\Phi$. As a reference also the damping for the traveling wave mode in the clean case with the same IBPA is depicted. The velocity wave is either stabilizing or destabilizing, depending on $\Delta\Phi$. For $\Delta\Phi = 0^\circ$ the velocity wave has just minor effects. Overall a sinusoidal dependence on the phase $\Delta\Phi$ is seen. The same qualitative dependency has the velocity wave with the amplitude $V_0 = 0.5m/s$ depicted in figure 16. The only qualitative difference is that for the sinus in this case the average damping lays nearer the clean cases value.

FIGURE 15: Damping parameter plotted against $\Delta\Phi$ for $\bar{\alpha} = 1^\circ$ and a fixed $IBPA$ of 51.4° .

With increasing velocity amplitude, also the effect on the stability rises. The differences to the reference damping increase with a higher velocity amplitude. This dependency is analysed further for the velocity wave case of $\Delta\Phi = 270^\circ$ with high dampening influence. Therefore, different amplitudes are simulated for this case. The resulting

FIGURE 16: Damping parameter plotted against $\Delta\Phi$ for $\bar{\alpha} = 1^\circ$ and a fixed IBPA of 51.4° .

damping parameters are shown in figure 17. The damping parameter decreases linearly with increasing amplitude up to $V_0 = 0.375\text{m/s}$. Also for increasing amplitudes starting from $V_0 = 0.625\text{m/s}$ a linear dependency is visible. In the linear flow regime, also the aerodynamic forces and moments increase with the incidence angle. That is the reason why the inhomogeneous inflow also needs to have an increasing effect to truly alter the aeroelastic stability. In figure 18 is the damping parameter plotted against the reciprocal torsional amplitude for the case $IBPA = 51.4^\circ$ and $\Delta\Phi = 270^\circ$. This leads to the conclusion that the velocity amplitude needs to increase linearly with increasing torsional amplitude to result in a nearly constant damping value.

FIGURE 17: Damping parameter plotted against velocity wave amplitude V_0 for IBPA of 51.4° , $\Delta\Phi = 270^\circ$ and $\bar{\alpha} = 1^\circ$.

Vortex around central streamline: The last inhomogeneous inflow presented is the x_a -vortex. The steady results show just insignificant change of the aeroelastic stability and are not illustrated. Thus the effects of the unsteady x_a -vortex can be related completely to the unsteady behaviour. The results for $\Delta\Phi = 90^\circ$ are shown in figure 19. The s-shape of the damping curve of the clean case is not changed by the inhomogeneous inflow. The damping

FIGURE 18: Damping parameter plotted against torsion amplitude $\bar{\alpha}$ for IBPA of 51.4° , $\Delta\Phi = 270^\circ$ and $V_0 = 0.5\text{m/s}$.

curve is shifted to higher damping parameters for spanwise positions lower than midspan ($z < 0.5s$) in this case. The vortex core, having no circumferential velocity, is convected to midspan. Consequently the damping is not changed here as seen in figure 19. For spanwise positions higher than midspan ($z > 0.5s$), the damping curve of the clean case is shifted to lower damping parameters, which means to higher aeroelastic stabilities. For analysed spanwise positions higher than 51% span the damping curves are completely in a stable regime.

FIGURE 19: Damping at different spanwise positions for inhomogeneous inflow condition with vortex around central streamline, $\Delta\Phi = 90^\circ$.

A change of the phase $\Delta\Phi$ to 135° results in smaller changes of the damping curve compared to the clean case, which is depicted in figure 20. For one thing, the results for the other simulated phases $\Delta\Phi$ show that the s-shape of the damping curve is not changed in any case. Secondly the results show a sinusoidal dependency of the damping parameter on the phase $\Delta\Phi$ for all spanwise positions and all inter blade phase angles. Thus for $\Delta\Phi = 0^\circ$ and $\Delta\Phi = 180^\circ$ no significant damping changes arises. For $\Delta\Phi = 90^\circ$

and $\Delta\Phi = 270^\circ$ the highest damping changes results. The damping curves for the unsteady x_a -vortex are reflected at the clean case damping curve for those two phases. However, the spanwise average damping, which is termed $\omega_{x_a}(t)\Sigma$ here, is not changed due to the unsteady x_a -vortex.

FIGURE 20: Damping at different spanwise positions for inhomogeneous inflow condition with vortex around central streamline, $\Delta\Phi = 135^\circ$.

FIGURE 21: Comparison between results of derived damping from TWM simulations and ICT.

The previous results for this inhomogeneous inflow are based on the influence coefficient technique. Additionally, the unsteady x_a -vortex is simulated in the traveling wave mode with $IBPA = 51.4^\circ$ for one $\Delta\Phi$. Here a x_a -vortex arrives at every blades leading edge, with the phase $\Delta\Phi = 135^\circ$ to the blades torsional oscillation. The results for the TWM simulations and the influence coefficient technique are compared for the unsteady x_a -vortex for the studied case of $IBPA = 51.4^\circ$ and $\Delta\Phi = 135^\circ$. It is the aim to show the differences of the methods in regard to the effects of the

inhomogeneous inflow. Therefore, the damping parameters differences to the midspan are compared. This is shown in figure 21. It is visible here that the damping curves have similar distributions starting from their midspan value. The predictions about the inhomogeneous inflow of the ICT are qualitatively good but have small quantitative differences.

FIGURE 22: $W_{dT}/(dx \cdot dz)$ at pressure side for $IBPA = 51.4^\circ$ and $\Delta\Phi = 135^\circ$.

FIGURE 23: $W_{dT}/(dx \cdot dz)$ at suction side for $IBPA = 51.4^\circ$ and $\Delta\Phi = 135^\circ$.

In figure 22 the aerodynamic work per area, done in one oscillation cycle, is plotted over the blades pressure surface. The coordinate x_c starts at the leading edge ($x_c = 0m$) and is going straight to trailing edge ($x_c = c$) and is applied here based on the chord length c . The aerodynamic work evaluates the aeroelastic stability neglecting the structural damping. This is a conservative approach, since increased structural damping also increases the aeroelastic stability. Positive aerodynamic work is equivalent to a potential unstable behaviour and negative work is equivalent to stable behaviour. The figures 22 and 23 show the influence of the x_a -vortex along the span which is consistent to the previous

results. The stability is decreased for spanwise positions up to midspan ($z < 0.5$) and increased for spanwise positions higher than midspan ($z > 0.5s$). Since the spanwise mean damping is not changed for the inhomogeneous inflow, it is a useful baseline along the chord. The highest effects on the stability are seen close to the leading edge for both suction and pressure side. Deviations from the spanwise mean damping are still visible up to the trailing edge, but they are of minor absolute values. This also underlines that it is an appropriate approach to define the phase $\Delta\Phi$ as the phase between the inhomogeneous inflow arriving at the leading edges of the blade row and the traveling wave mode.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The influence of variable inflow conditions on the aeroelastic stability has been investigated. For this purpose numerical simulations have been performed with the geometry of the compressor cascade of the aeroelastic test rig at the Chair for Aero Engines at the Technische Universität Berlin. The stationary inflow conditions have nearly no effect on the aeroelastic stability. On the contrary the unsteady inflow conditions significantly influence the aerodynamic damping. For the unsteady velocity wave, the quantitatively highest difference in aeroelastic damping is calculated. The driving parameter is the phase between total pressure wave and traveling wave mode. The damping depends on the phase in a sinusoidal way. Furthermore the amplitude of this sinus depends nearly linearly on the ratio of velocity wave amplitude to vibration amplitude in the simulated cases. For the unsteady vortex around the central streamline, a dependency of the spanwise position is observed, but the spanwise average of the aeroelastic stability is not changed. For every spanwise position, the difference of the damping parameter to the clean case stays similar for all inter blade phase angles. The analysis of the 3D distribution of the aerodynamic work shows the highest impact on aeroelastic stability on the leading edge. The results are a basis for possible active flutter control.

NOMENCLATURE

c	chord length
C_M	influence coefficient
$\underline{\underline{D}}$	damping matrix
f_θ	torsional frequency
g	damping parameter
g_{str}	mechanical damping
h	wake position $14 \cdot y(x=0)/\Delta Y$
I_θ	torsional inertia per span
$IBPA$	inter blade phase angle
k	reduced frequency
$\underline{\underline{K}}$	stiffness matrix
m	blade number
$\underline{\underline{M}}$	mass matrix
M	aerodynamic moment

n	nodal diameter
N	number of blades
r	distance to vortex core
r_0	Rankine vortex
r_θ^2	inertia parameter
s	span
s_a	distance from origin to leading edge
t	time
T	oscillation period
V	inlet velocity
$V_{x,a}$	velocity in x_a -direction
V_0	velocity amplitude
V_m	mean inlet velocity
V_θ	circumferential velocity
W_{dT}	aerodynamic work
x	CFD-coordinate
x_a	aerodynamic coordinate
y	CFD-coordinate
y_a	aerodynamic coordinate
ΔY	distance of two leading edges of adjacent blades
z	CFD-coordinate
α	angle of attack
γ	stagger angle
Γ	unsteady circulation
Γ_0	steady circulation
θ	torsional angle
$\bar{\theta}$	torsional angle amplitude
λ	frequency parameter
μ	density ratio
ρ	density
Φ_{tot}	phase convection term
$\Delta\Phi$	phase between unsteady inhomogeneous inflow arriving at leading edge and blade oscillation
ω	eigenfrequency
ω_θ	torsion eigenfrequency

Abbreviations

TWM	traveling wave mode
IBPA	inter blade phase angle
ICT	influence coefficient technique
CFD	computational fluid dynamics

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